

Synchronous Endometrial and Ovarian Tumors: Diagnostic Challenges and the Role of Integrated Molecular Classification – A Case Report

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Abstract

Background: Synchronous endometrial and ovarian tumors (SEOC) are rare, representing approximately 3–10% of gynecologic cancers [1]. They are defined by the simultaneous occurrence of malignant tumors in both the endometrium and the ovary and constitute the most common form of synchronous gynecologic malignancies [2,3]. It's associated with a better prognosis than metastatic forms affecting a single organ [4].

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 49-year-old nulligravid woman with a family history of colorectal cancer in a first-degree relative. She presented with chronic pelvic pain. Clinical examination was unremarkable. Pelvic ultrasound revealed endometrial thickening of 15 mm with an intracavitary lesion, a left solid-cystic adnexal mass with papillary projections, a cystic right ovary, and minimal ascites. Serum CA-125 level was elevated at 357 IU/mL.

Pelvic magnetic resonance imaging confirmed a non-invasive endometrial mass and bilateral ovarian masses suspicious for malignancy, associated with moderate ascites without visible peritoneal implants. Diagnostic hysteroscopy and laparoscopy revealed an exophytic endometrial mass, an enlarged exophytic left ovary, a cystic right ovary, and ascites. Endometrial, ovarian, and peritoneal biopsies suggested a FIGO stage II endometrioid endometrial carcinoma associated with an undifferentiated ovarian carcinoma, FIGO stage IC.

The patient underwent total hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy, pelvic and para-aortic lymphadenectomy, omentectomy, and appendectomy. Final pathology confirmed an endometrioid carcinoma infiltrating two-thirds of the myometrium, bilateral ovarian involvement, and omental carcinomatosis, with negative lymph nodes and positive ascitic cytology (pT3c).

Postoperative pathological staging was performed according to the pTNM classification, resulting in a final stage of pT3c.

Four cycles of adjuvant chemotherapy were administered, with no evidence of recurrence on follow-up imaging.

Conclusion: SEOC remains a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge. Accurate diagnosis requires an integrated approach combining histopathology, molecular analysis, and clinical features to guide optimal management.

More Information

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Introduction

Synchronous endometrial and ovarian tumors (SEOC) are rare, occurring in approximately 3–10% of patients with gynecologic malignancies [1]. These tumors are defined by the simultaneous involvement of both the endometrium and the ovary by malignant disease. Synchronous endometrial and ovarian cancer (SEOC) is the most common form of synchronous gynecologic cancers, accounting for 50–70% of all cases, and is characterized by the coexistence of endometrial and ovarian cancers at the time of diagnosis [2,3].

Case Presentation

We report the case of a 49-year-old nulligravid woman with no significant medical history, who presented with chronic pelvic pain evolving over six months. Her family history was notable for a brother who died from colorectal cancer at the age of 43. Clinical examination was unremarkable; the abdomen was soft, and a vaginal examination was not performed.

Pelvic ultrasound revealed endometrial thickening measuring 15 mm associated with an intracavitary lesion, as well as bilateral adnexal abnormalities: a left solid-cystic mass with papillary projections and an enlarged right ovary with cystic content. A small amount of ascites was also observed. Serum CA-125 level was elevated at 357 IU/mL.

Magnetic resonance imaging confirmed an endometrial mass measuring 67 mm with diffusion hyperintensity, without myometrial invasion or cervical stromal involvement. Both ovaries showed suspicious masses, more prominent on the left, with solid components and diffusion restriction. Moderate ascites was present, with no visible peritoneal implants.

Diagnostic hysteroscopy combined with laparoscopy was performed. Hysteroscopy revealed an exophytic endocavitary mass and endometrium with irregular vascularization. Laparoscopy showed an enlarged, exophytic left ovary, a cystic right ovary, and a small volume of ascites. Endometrial, ovarian, and peritoneal biopsies were obtained.

Thoraco-abdomino-pelvic computed tomography performed for staging purposes showed no distant metastases. After multidisciplinary discussion, the patient was diagnosed with FIGO stage II endometrioid endometrial carcinoma associated with an undifferentiated ovarian carcinoma, FIGO stage IC, and radical surgery was indicated.

Total hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy, pelvic and para-aortic lymphadenectomy, omentectomy, and appendectomy confirmed an endometrioid carcinoma infiltrating two-thirds of the myometrium, with bilateral ovarian involvement and omental carcinomatosis. Lymph nodes were negative, and ascitic fluid cytology was positive. The final pathological stage was pT3c.

The patient received four cycles of adjuvant chemotherapy with favorable evolution. Follow-up computed tomography in July 2025 showed no residual tumor or metastatic disease.

Discussion

Distinguishing synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian tumors from metastatic disease is crucial, as it directly impacts diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis [5]. Synchronous tumors represent two independent primary neoplasms, whereas metastatic forms result from the spread of a primary tumor from one organ to the other [6,7].

Despite the presence of omental involvement, the diagnosis of synchronous endometrial and ovarian tumors was retained based on clinicopathological features and the absence of distant metastatic disease, in line with recent molecular and prognostic approaches.

From a diagnostic perspective: Since the 1980s, several histopathological criteria have been proposed to differentiate these entities. Ulbright and Roth (1985) defined major and minor criteria suggestive of metastatic disease, including multinodular ovarian involvement, bilaterality, small ovarian size (<5 cm), and deep myometrial invasion [8]. Scully et al. (1999) further refined these criteria, emphasizing tumor size discrepancy, multiple superficial implants, and transtubal spread [9].

From a molecular standpoint More recently, genomic and whole-exome sequencing analyses have improved understanding of the relationship between these tumors. Several studies have demonstrated shared somatic mutations and clonal alterations, suggesting a common tumor origin with dissemination between sites [10,11]. However, low-grade and early-stage tumors often exhibit indolent behavior, remaining confined to a shared microenvironment without distant metastases [12].

Lynch syndrome represents a significant risk factor for SEOC [13]. Although the exact correlation remains incompletely understood, mutations in DNA mismatch repair (MMR) genes characteristic of Lynch syndrome may predispose to the simultaneous development of endometrial and ovarian cancers. Given the association with colorectal, endometrial, and ovarian cancers, genetic screening for Lynch syndrome is recommended in patients with a relevant family history [14].

Although genetic testing was not performed in this patient, the family history of early-onset colorectal cancer raises the possibility of Lynch syndrome and supports the relevance of molecular evaluation in similar cases.

Molecular analysis of SEOC, including microsatellite instability (MSI) testing and MMR gene mutation analysis, contributes to tailored management and familial genetic counseling [14,15].

From a therapeutic and prognostic perspective in the context of SEOC, the 2023 FIGO classification represents a major advance by integrating histopathological and molecular data beyond anatomical staging alone [16]. The 2023 Saint-Paul-de-Vence recommendations propose an integrated prognostic approach guiding adjuvant treatment based on molecular profiles rather than solely on anatomical stage [17]. This evolution, based on TCGA classification (POLE, MSI, p53, NSMP), is particularly relevant in SEOC, where molecular characterization aids in distinguishing true synchronous tumors from metastatic disease and in guiding personalized management [16–18].

Overall, patients with SEOC have a better prognosis than those with metastatic disease. Management primarily relies on complete surgical staging, followed, when necessary, by adjuvant therapy determined by postoperative histopathological findings. Standard surgery includes total hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy, omentectomy, pelvic and para-aortic lymphadenectomy, and appendectomy [19].

The indication for adjuvant treatment—chemotherapy and, less frequently, radiotherapy—is individualized based on stage, grade, and histological characteristics [20]. Chemotherapy is commonly recommended, particularly because of the ovarian component, with 60–80% of patients receiving adjuvant treatment in reported series [21].

Fertility-sparing options are limited in SEOC compared with isolated cancers, and data remain scarce. Management should therefore be individualized, taking into account tumor characteristics and the patient's reproductive wishes [20].

Conclusion

Synchronous endometrial and ovarian tumors represent a complex diagnostic and therapeutic entity. Accurate differentiation from metastatic disease requires an integrated approach combining histopathology, molecular profiling, and clinical context. Recent evidence supports the central role of molecular classification in refining diagnosis, guiding treatment decisions, and improving prognostic stratification.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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